

INDEPENDENT WORK AS A FORM OF LEARNERS' COGNITIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the issue of effective organization of learners' independent work aimed at developing their cognitive and creative activities.*

Keywords: *independent work, cognitive activity, creative activity, reflectivity, self-discipline, self-regulation, self-improvement.*

САМОСТОЯТЕЛЬНАЯ РАБОТА КАК ФОРМА ПРОЯВЛЕНИЯ ПОЗНАВАТЕЛЬНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ УЧАЩИХСЯ ШКОЛЫ

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена проблеме эффективной организации самостоятельной работы учащихся, направленной на развитие их познавательной и творческой деятельности.*

Ключевые слова: *самостоятельная работа, познавательная деятельность, творческая деятельность, рефлексивность, самодисциплина, саморегуляция, самосовершенствование.*

INTRODUCTION

The concept of “independent work” is interpreted differently in the psychological and pedagogical literature. The most common is the interpretation of the concept of “independent work” given by V.N. Orlov, who believes that independent work is a learner's constantly manifested ability to achieve the goal of activity without others help.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In our opinion, the concept of A. I. Zimnyaya is also appropriate, considering that independent work is a purposeful, internally motivated, structured type of learner's activity, “the implementation of which requires the organization of a sufficiently high level of reflectivity, self-discipline, personal responsibility of the student in which he will receive satisfaction as the process of self-improvement and self-knowledge” [2; p.156]. In this approach, the scientist takes into account the unity of the following components of independent activity: self-regulation, self-activation, self-organization, self-control, etc.

A.I. Zimnyaya believes that independent work is associated with the learning process and is a consequence of the correct organization of educational and cognitive activities at school. She emphasizes that the learner's independent work is a consequence of his/her properly organized learning activities in the classroom.

Independent work is, on the one hand, an educational task, on the other hand, a form of manifestation of the corresponding activity: memory, thinking, creative imagination when the student completes the educational task, which, ultimately, leads the learner either to obtain new, previously unknown knowledge or to deepen and expand the scope of already acquired knowledge.

Consequently, independent work is such a teaching tool that “in each specific situation of assimilation corresponds to a specific didactic goal and task of the lesson; forms learner's necessary volume and level of knowledge, skills and abilities for solving cognitive problems and correspondingly moving from the lower to the higher levels of mental activity; develops

students' psychological attitude towards independent systematic replenishment of their knowledge and the development of skills to navigate the flow of scientific and social information while solving new cognitive problems" [6; p.128].

Nowadays, the role of independent work of schoolchildren is increasing due to the change in the purpose of education, its focus on the formation of skills, creative activity, with the computerization of education.

Independent work of learners included in the learning process, is work that is performed without the direct participation of the teacher, but on his/her instructions at a time specially provided for this. At the same time, learners consciously strive to achieve the goal, using their efforts to express their mental abilities.

Independent work also involves learners' active mental actions associated with the search for the most rational ways to complete tasks, with an analysis of the results of work.

"Independent work, according to the methodologists of Uzbekistan Z.K. Kudasheva and S.S. Magdiyeva, is not final in itself, it is a means of deepening learners' solid knowledge, a means of forming their activity and independence, developing their mental abilities" [5; p.120].

A learner who crosses the threshold of a school for the first time cannot independently set the goal of his/her activity and is not able to plan his/her actions yet, correct their implementation, and correlate the result obtained with the goal set. However, while studying at school, he/she must gradually reach a certain level of independence, which reveals his potential opportunities.

RESULTS

It is obvious that the inclusion of independent work in the content of the lessons is an urgent need, so the teacher must correctly build pupils' activities while maximizing the use of their internal reserves.

"The content of independent work includes task analysis, work planning, task completion, verification and evaluation of completed work. Individual types of independent work may include either all or some of these elements. The more of these elements are included in the pupils' independent work, the higher its level, and hence the level of independence of schoolchildren, the development of which is one of the main goals of organizing independent work in the classroom" [3; p.27].

The ultimate goal of the formation of pupils' independent activity is to achieve such a level of development when they are able to independently set a goal, update the knowledge and methods of action necessary to solve the problem; when they can independently plan their actions.

Today, the following provisions accepted in methodological science are indisputable:

1. An increase in the degree of independence is achieved through such a construction of teaching and learning during which the transition is made from the teacher's instructions to the need to use certain knowledge and actions in solving a learning problem to an independent search for such knowledge and actions.

2. The formation of the educational activity of schoolchildren should provide such organization of work where learners move from the formation of individual operations of the actions performed to the formation of the entire action.

3. The degree of pupils' independence will also increase if they pass from mastering actions in a ready-made form to independently discovering individual actions and their systems.

4. Increasing the degree of independence should mean the transition of pupils from the awareness of the need to master this specific skill to the awareness of the importance of mastering the integral structure of educational activity.

5. The transition from tasks of a reproductive nature to creative tasks that require the use of knowledge and actions of an interdisciplinary nature also contributes to the formation of pupils' independence [1; p.33].

An important role of pupils' activities is played by independent work with a textbook, its text, illustrations, maps, etc.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of independent work with a book may be to get acquainted with its structure, skim through, read individual chapters, search for answers to certain questions, study the material, referencing individual passages of text or the entire book, solving examples and problems, performing control tests, and finally, memorizing material on memory.

The most widespread are two types of work with the book: in the classroom under the guidance of a teacher and at home in order to consolidate and expand the knowledge gained in the lesson. When preparing pupils to work with a book, the teacher indicates with which previously studied material it is necessary to compare or combine new educational material. If the work is carried out in the classroom, then the entire process of studying the material from the book is divided into separate parts, the implementation of which is controlled. After reading a passage of text, students, at the direction of the teacher, stop and perform the necessary actions: understand, remember, compare, contrast, etc.

Learners' work with the text of the textbook at home begins with the reproduction from memory of the knowledge gained in the lesson.

Synthesizing the educational material learned in the lesson with the text of the textbook is the most important condition for rational work with the book. When reading a book, pupils should develop a memorization mindset. Therefore, it is necessary to teach them to catch the order of presentation and, as they read, mentally draw up a plan for what they read. In this regard, the work of drawing up a plan or writing down the main idea of the book in the form of theses is of great help. Learning to work with a book involves the formation of learners' self-control skills. It is necessary to ensure that he/she argues about the knowledge of the material not by how many times he has read the text of the textbook, but by the ability to consciously and in detail state the content of what he has read. To do this, it is necessary to form the habit of devoting more time not to reading the material, but to actively recalling it from memory.

Work with a textbook at the lesson is most often organized by a teacher: work on studying new material, work on consolidating new knowledge, working with a textbook with a generalizing repetition of the material covered, etc. During a lesson, a pupil under the supervision of a teacher acquires skills of working with a book, which will then be useful for him/her in self-study. At the first stage of learners' self-education it is necessary to instill a desire to become interested in various literature.

The next stage in the formation of skills and abilities to work with a book can be the teacher's work on the purposeful development of such components of work with the printed word as the ability to highlight the main idea that leads the idea in the text. Having mastered this skill, which is important for the ability to work with a printed source, you can prepare pupils to learn

how to plan reading the text. This will help them learn to identify the internal structure of the text, divide it into parts and give them appropriate headings [5; p.73].

The third component of the organization of pupils' independent activity is the formation their ability under the guidance of a teacher to draw up a summary, theses, etc. Having overcome important stages (three) under the guidance of a teacher the pupil will gradually develop the ability to work with a book. He/she will be able to fully use such skills and abilities as a quick preview of the entire content, full reading, underlining the main thing, analyzing the plot and composition of the text, drawing up a preliminary plan or writing out the main ideas, supporting questions, presentation plan in preparation for retelling depending on the goal. reading, skimming of what has been read, etc. Note that work with a textbook must be used at all stages of the educational process.

Independent work with didactic material is also widely used. Didactic material can be of three types: one – serving to consolidate and repeat the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by children, therefore, compiled according to the program; the other is propaedeutic in content, also drawn up according to the program, but leading learners forward and helping them to assimilate the material being studied more easily and quickly; the third – not related to the program, but expanding the horizons of pupils, arousing their interest in knowledge, instilling a love for mental work. Recently, independent work on such material as an educational film and television programs has begun to spread.

Creative independent work is the main one in the system of independent activity of schoolchildren, which allows them to acquire fundamentally new knowledge, consolidates the skills of independent search for knowledge.

Psychologists (P.Ya. Galperin, L.S. Vygotsky and others) believe that the mental activity of schoolchildren in solving creative problems is in many respects similar to the mental activity of creative and scientific workers. Tasks of this type are one of the most effective means of shaping creative personalities. We adhere to this point of view, since our observations in practice have shown the legitimacy of such provisions. Today, curricula designed for secondary education are aimed at such an improvement in education, which is aimed at the comprehensive development of pupils' independence, active assimilation of knowledge. The mental activity of pupils should be connected with their practical activities; Only in this case, they will acquire knowledge, understanding its significance. Consequently, independent work develops schoolchildren's cognitive abilities: observation, inquisitiveness, logical thinking, memory, imagination, and creative activity.

The peculiarity of independent work is that that setting a certain task for pupils, the teacher gives opportunity for pupils to fulfill it independently, assuming the process of indispensable connection of pupils' independent thought with the independent performance of mental actions. Therefore, independent work should be organized as the performance of certain tasks on which pupils work without the direct participation of the teacher: they independently comprehend the task on the basis of a specific text.

CONCLUSIONS

Independent work can be organized at various levels: from reproducing actions according to a model and recognizing objects by comparing them with a known model to compiling a model and algorithm of actions in non-standard learning situations. When compiling assignments

for independent work, one should take into account the degree of their complexity, which should correspond to the educational capabilities of schoolchildren.

The transition from one level to another is carried out gradually, only when it is possible to be convinced that the student will cope with the next level of independence, otherwise, in an atmosphere of haste and nervousness, the learner may experience gaps in knowledge.

It is very important that the content of independent work, the form and time of its implementation meet the main goals of teaching this topic at a certain stage of studying the educational process.

When compiling a lesson model, it is important for the teacher to carefully consider the place and time of independent work, clearly define its general content, and divide tasks into different levels of complexity.

It should also be remembered that the mood of the teacher himself has a great influence on the learners' success, therefore it is very important to be able to create a friendly atmosphere in the classroom in time, especially during independent work.

REFERENCES

1. Ефремов А.Ю. Нравственная самоорганизация личности в педагогическом сообществе: Учеб. пособие. – Воронеж, Воронеж. гос. пед. ун-т, 1999.
2. Зимняя И.А. Педагогическая психология [Текст] / И.А. Зимняя. – Учебник для вузов. – Москва: «Логос», 2004.
3. Казакова А.Г. Организация самостоятельной работы школьников [Текст] / А.Г. Казакова. – Москва: МГУКИ, 2005.
4. Кудашева З.К., Магдиева С.С. Методика обучения литературы. Учебное пособие для студентов ВОУ. Алокачи, 2008.
5. Магдиева С. С., Лагай Е.А. Современные педагогические технологии на уроках русского языка и литературы. Учебное пособие для учителей общеобразовательных школ Узбекистана. – Ташкент, 2021.
6. Петровский В.А. Личность в психологии: парадигма субъектности. – Ростов-на-Дону, «Феникс», 1996.